

ZH3, a high-yielding and multide-resistance rice for single- or double-cropping in South China

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ZH3 is a high-yielding japonica with medium duration, resistance to blast (BI) and lodging, wide adaptability, and moderate resistance to bacterial blight (BB). Since its release in 1990, ZH3 has been planted in double- and single-cropped areas of South China.

ZH3 was selected from a cross between medium line 84-35 (Torede 1 ///Aijing 14/Keqing 3///Jinlei 440) and Xiushui 04, a local popular modern

Table 1. Yield potential of ZH3 in China, 1989. ^a

Site	Double-cropped		Single-cropped	
	Yield (t/ha)	Increase over check (%)	Yield (t/ha)	Increase over check (%)
Hangzhou, Zhejiang	7.9	5.7*	9.1	10.5**
Zhenjiang, Jiangsu	6.8	3.1	8.8	2.2
Wuhu, Anhui	6.7	2.9	8.0	8.7**
Xiaogan, Huban	6.9	4.2	8.7	5.8*

^a Significant at 5% (*) and 1% levels (**).

variety in Zhejiang Province. It yielded 6.7-7.9 t/ha in double-cropped areas and 8-9.1 t/ha in single-cropped areas. These yields exceeded those of local check Varieties by 2.2-10.5% at four sites in South China (Table 1).

Average growth duration of ZH3 was 134 d in double-cropped areas and 158 d

Table 2. Resistance of ZH3 to BI and BB. Zhejiang, China, 1989 and 1990. ^a

Entry	Score	
	BI	BB
1989		
ZH3	1	3
Xiushui 48 (check)	3	5
1990		
ZH3	1	3
Xiushui 48 (check)	3	5

^a By the Standard evaluation system for rice.

in single-cropped areas in Zhejiang. Its gene for BI resistance comes from Torede 1, Pi-z¹ (Table 2).

ZH3 is semidwarf (about 82.5 cm). It has dense panicles that are about 15.2 cm long, 74.8 grains/panicle, 90.9% seed fertility, and 1,000-grain weight of 26.5 g. □

Irrigated germplasm improvement—deepwater

Three varieties of floating rice released to farmers in Cambodia

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The floating rice area in Cambodia has declined from 390,000 to about 110,000 ha. Reasons for the decline were the policies of the ruling regime from 1974 to 1979, the security situation after 1979, and the loss of floating varieties. An urgent system of introducing varieties and breeding lines and testing them in multilocation trials was adopted in 1986.

Varieties Tewada, Khao Tah Petch, and HTAFR77022-45-3-2-1 (Don) were very promising in advanced yield trials (AYT) and in on-farm adaptive trials (OFAT) during 1989 and 1990 (Table 1). In the OFATs, these varieties were given to farmers in 1990 to test in their fields under their own cultural practices, crop management style, and constraints. Five of the nine sets of OFAT were successfully completed. Farmers preferred the new varieties over their old ones (Table 2) for reasons including better survival, stable yield, desired maturity across locations, and superior grain type. Seed multiplication is under way. □

Table 1. Performance of promising varieties in advanced yield trials of floating rice in Cambodia, 1989 and 1990.

Variety	Av yield (t/ha)		Agronomical character, 1990					
	1989 ^a	1990 ^b	Height (cm)	Panicle length (cm)	Flowering date	Duration (d)	Grains/panicle (no.)	PAcp ^d score
Don	1.23	1.87	218	26	30 Nov	201	122	4.2
Khao Tah Petch	1.29	1.43	207	26	28 Nov	192	104	3.9
Tewada	1.00	1.67	201	25	25 Nov	195	104	4.3
Local check	1.22	1.88	223	24	29 Nov	202	158	3.0

^a Av over 4 locations. ^b Av over 6 locations. ^c Av over 7 locations. ^d Phenotypic acceptability.

Table 2. Yield of promising varieties in 5 farmers' fields (OFAT) in Cambodia, 1990. ^a

Variety	Yield (t/ha)				
	Kok Bantey, Rolear Phaer, Kampong Chhnang	Trapeang Veng, Kampong Chhnang	Trapeang Chan, Kampong Chhnang	Toul Koktrap, Svay Rieng	Mokda, Romeas Hek, Svay Rieng
Don	0.5	0.3	1.2	—	1.4
Khao Tah Petch	0.6	2.1	0.8	4.4	1.0
Tewada	0.5	1.6	0.7	4.5	1.0
Local check	0.8	4.6	0.8	2.1	0.9

^a Farmers' choice variety.

Surveys of disease or insect incidence/severity in one environment are useful only if the information is related to other variables (e.g., climatic factors, crop intensification, cultivars, management practices, etc.). By itself, information on incidence in one environment does not increase scientific knowledge.